

IAM4NFDI

Service description, operating concept & TOMs

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Note: The English version of this document is authoritative; the German translation is for information purposes only.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Motivation for this document

This document specifies the consulting, support and operating services that will be provided as part of the IAM4NFDI project to the Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V. and in particular to the associated NFDI consortia.

It describes the productive state to be achieved during the IAM4NFDI project. During the project period, subsets of these services will be offered to the consortia free of charge. After the end of the project, the services will need to be financed in a sustainable way, for example through contracts with the individual consortia or by a superordinate institution.

For this later phase, this document can be used as a basis for support contracts and will become part of each contract. In particular, those parts of this document that are explicitly mentioned in the respective 'Service Offer' are part of the contract.

In summary, this includes consulting, support and operating services. A general section gives an overview and describes the components to be operated. These are the central components NFDI Infrastructure Proxy and NFDI Community Attribute Authority as well as the four different offers for the implementation of a Community AAI. The following chapters describe the three different kinds of services in detail. The text is supplemented by appendices describing the SLAs and other specifics promised by each service provider. These appendices are also referenced in tenders and thus will become part of the contract. Finally, this document contains sample contracts based on the EVB-IT contracts.

All important terms are explained in 1.3 Definition of used terms.

1.2. Contractual relationships and legal entities in the context of the NFDI-AAI

The NFDI is a complex structure. Therefore, the different actors and the contractual relationships between them are described below. The architecture of the NFDI-AAI¹ serves as a guideline:

¹ See in detail at <https://doc.nfdi-aa1.de/architecture/>

Figure 1 – NFDI-AAI Architecture

In the context of contractual relationships, three levels can be roughly distinguished in the NFDI-AAI:

1. National Federations, independent authentication services and interfaces to community AAs (see 1.3 Definition of used terms)
2. Community AAs and interfaces to infrastructure proxies
3. infrastructure proxies as well as connected services and infrastructures, although the latter are not being the subject of these considerations.

A structure-forming criterion here is the point at which NFDI-relevant resources/services are integrated as a service provider (SP):

- Generic Service: Level 1
- Community Service: Level 2
- NFDI Infrastructure Service: Level 3

Level 1:

The “eduGAIN” Cloud represents the 79 National Federations currently (February 2024) participating in the eduGAIN Interfederation². In the case of Germany, this is the DFN-AAI³ operated by the DFN-Verein (see 1.3 Definition of used terms), in which currently about 400 universities, colleges and other publicly funded and non-profit research institutions as well as numerous commercial and non-commercial service providers with a research focus participate. DFN-Verein as federation operator acts as a trust anchor or trusted third party. In this role, it closes contracts with all participating institutions and service providers.

The participating institutions operate a so-called Identity Provider (IdP) as an authentication service for their members. In addition, they are entitled to also participate in DFN-AAI and eduGAIN with any number of service providers. This requires a service agreement. The requirements are documented on the DFN-Verein website⁴. Pure service providers close a service provider agreement with DFN-Verein, which is free of charge.

A *Generic Service* can therefore be registered in the DFN-AAI and eduGAIN by a participating institution that is a partner in at least one NFDI consortium - or by any other legal entity that must close at least one service provider agreement with DFN-Verein.

The cloud with the symbols of Google, ORCID, etc. stands for authentication services operated by these providers. This category of authentication services is often referred to as “social ID” or “social login”. Contractual relationships exist exclusively between the operators of these platforms and the end users.

The edu-ID proxy is a service of the DFN-AAI. In order to connect the SP-components of the Community AAls (CAAI) with the IdP-component of the edu-ID-Proxy, the legal entity operating or having a CAAI operated must also close at least one service provider agreement with the DFN-Verein.

Level 2:

With regard to Community AAls, it can be assumed that they operate under the responsibility of a legal entity representing the research consortium or the communities represented by it. This can be, for example, a university or research institution - or the consortium itself (see 1.2.5 Legal form of research alliances).

The integration of *community services* to a CAAI, their operation and the management of virtual organisations in the CAAI are generally carried out within the framework of the policy framework of the NFDI-AAI⁵. Further contractual relationships going beyond this are possible but are not the subject of this document.

² <https://technical.edugain.org>

³ <https://doku.tid.dfn.de/en:dfnaai:start>

⁴ <https://www.dfn.de/dienste/entgelte/> (German only)

⁵ <https://doc.nfdi-aai.de/policies/>

The technical operation of a CAAI instance and the associated consulting and support services provided by one of the project partners listed below are the subject of the following chapters.

Level 3:

Level 3 is defined by the core components of the NFDI Infrastructure Proxy and possibly the NFDI Community Attribute Authority (AA). The connection of the *NFDI Infrastructure Services* to the NFDI Infrastructure Proxy and access to them via the CAAIs can take place within the framework of the NFDI-AAI Policy Framework. A separate federation operated by DFN-Verein currently serves as the connecting infrastructure. Since all participating legal entities are already members of the DFN-AAI to date, no further contractual arrangements are necessary at present.

The connection to other infrastructures, such as the EOSC AAI, is subject to the contracts and policies of these infrastructures.

The long-term operation of the two central components and the associated consulting and support services by the project partners mentioned below should be contractually regulated with a superordinate body – e.g. with NFDI e.V. – and not with individual consortia or legal entities representing them.

1.2.1. NFDI consortia and Base4NFDI

The NFDI comprises 26 research consortia (as of December 14th, 2023) and the Base4NFDI consortium. The consortia cover a wide range of scientific disciplines: from cultural studies, social sciences, humanities and engineering to life sciences and nature sciences. The consortia are formed by various organisations (members), mostly universities or other scientific institutions.

The “Base4NFDI” consortium provides and operates generic services for all NFDI consortia.

In theory, contractors can be the individual consortia among themselves, as well as individual consortia and Base4NFDI.

1.2.2. DFN-Verein and DFN-AAI

For the role of DFN-Verein as federation operator and the contractual aspects of DFN-AAI, see above, section 1.2., on level 1.

Regarding the central components of level 3 (infra-proxy, AA), DFN-Verein could in principle take over the operation of these components and the associated consulting and support services in the long term. These services could either be integrated into service portfolio of DFN-AAI as a further component – in this case at no additional cost – or as a chargeable additional service if this service feature is only relevant for a small proportion of DFN-Verein's subscribers. This is a decision to be made by the committees of DFN. In any case, contractual arrangements in this regard should be made with a superordinate authority as described above.

Irrespective of this, DFN-Verein can provide a contractual framework for the services and scenarios described in the following chapters, within which individual services can be ordered

and billed flexibly by any project partner. The so-called Federated Services of DFN-Verein serve as a model for this.

1.2.3 Local IdP operators

Local IdP operators are the (home) institutions (usually universities or other research institutions) where the primary user account of the researcher is held. This account usually allows them to use the IT services of their home institution.

In addition, other institutions offer IT services for widespread use in academic contexts, where access and permissions to use these services are controlled by authentication and authorisation infrastructures (AAI, e.g. DFN-AAI or other federations from eduGAIN). In order to be able to participate in an AAI, a (local) Identity Provider (IdP) is operated at the home institutions.

In the context of IAM4NFDI, it is assumed that users of IT services for the NFDI can be regularly authenticated with a user account at a local IdP in their home institution. The IdP can either be part of an existing AAI (DFN-AAI or other federations from eduGAIN) or be connected to the community AAI of an NFDI consortium as a so-called homeless or guest IdP.

In order to use IT services in the NFDI, the local IdP transmits personal data such as first name, last name, e-mail address and a unique identifier to the operator of the desired IT service (usually only with the consent of the user for data protection reasons). The data is transferred in accordance with the applicable policies of the parent AAI, the Community AAI (CAAI) and the NFDI AAI. Typically, IdP operators conclude bilateral contracts with service providers specifying the services and conditions of use (e.g. licences), as well as the personal data (attributes) to be transferred for their use. NFDI consortia or the operators of consortium specific services may act as service providers in such contractual relationships.

1.2.4 IAM4NFDI project group

IAM4NFDI is a project of the Base4NFDI consortium and aims to

- provide an overarching AAI solution for the NFDI consortia and the NFDI as a whole,
- ensure compatibility with external/international projects and partners (use of the AARC Blueprint Architecture, compatibility with the EOSC AAI), and
- ensure the operation of the NFDI-AAI solution during the project period in accordance with the service description/operation concept specified in this document.

The IAM4NFDI project group consists of the following partners:

- RWTH Aachen
- DFN-Verein
- DAASI International
- Forschungszentrum Jülich
- Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung Göttingen (GWDG)
- Karlsruher Institut für Technologie (KIT)
- Rheinland-Pfälzische Technische Universität Kaiserslautern-Landau

1.2.5 Legal form of research alliances

In the context of IAM4NFDI services, research groups are the main actors (the research consortia, Base4NFDI and its sub-group IAM4NFDI). A research consortium is characterised by a common purpose and a common governance structure. Even though such alliances are usually composed of institutions with a public law character (universities, research institutes, etc.), they are – if no other legal form is found – to be considered in Germany as a “Gesellschaft bürgerlichen Rechts” (GbR) “and would then quickly qualify as an external GbR” (Eberbach et al. 2017, p. 2). The GbR form in turn means that all institutions involved in the association are jointly and severally liable. This cannot be circumvented by “denial of legal form” clauses in the association agreement (ibid.). A brief overview of possible legal forms in addition to the GbR, essentially (g)GmbH, registered association (e.V.) and foundation, can be found in (Eberbach 2018, chapter 3). (Lappe 2019) analyses these different legal forms for cooperation between academic institutions and concludes that there is no truly suitable legal form for this purpose. Eberbach and Lappe therefore call for better legal regulation.

On 1 January 2024, new legal regulations (MoPeG) for GbRs came into force, which promise better legal certainty. A distinction is now no longer made between external and internal GbRs, but between a GbR having legal capacity and a GbR not having legal capacity, whereby only the former can participate in legal transactions and can therefore also become a contractual partner in principle. “What is new is that the GbR only comes into existence in relation to third parties as soon as it participates in legal transactions with the consent of all partners, but at the latest when it is entered in the company register” (IHK Stuttgart 2023). It is therefore now a declared act of all association participants that the association becomes legally capable. Even if this probably does not completely eliminate the legal uncertainty postulated by Eberhard and Lappe, it represents a clear step in this direction for research networks. To summarise: if the participants in a research consortium jointly declare themselves to be a GbR having legal capacity and register it in a company register introduced as part of the MoPeG, it could enter into contracts. This would apply to all NFDI consortia as well as Base4NFDI and IAM4NFDI. As long as this does not happen, other regulations must be found, such as by the NFDI Association as a contract broker.

Literature:

- Eberbach et al. 2017: Eberbach, Wolfram; Hommelhoff, Peter, Lappe Johannes: Eine Kooperationsform für die Wissenschaft. In *Ordnung der Wissenschaft 2017*, S. 1-12. https://ordnungderwissenschaft.de/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Gesamtausgabe_2017_odw_ordnung_der_wissenschaft.pdf
- Eberbach 2018: Eberbach, Wolfram: Eine Rechtsform für Wissenschaftskooperationen – Ausgangspunkte und Grundlagen –. In: *Ordnung der Wissenschaft 2018*, S. 51-68. https://ordnungderwissenschaft.de/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/OdW_Jahresausgabe_2018.pdf
- IHK Stuttgart 2023: IHK Region Stuttgart: Modernisierung der Gesellschaft bürgerlichen Rechts (GbR). Stand Dezember 2023. <https://www.ihk.de/stuttgart/fuer-unternehmen/recht-und-steuern/gesellschaftsrecht-unternehmensformen/wahl-der->

rechtsform-gesellschaftsrecht/gbr/modernisierung-gesellschaft-buergerlichen-rechts-gbr-5817748

- Lappe 2019: Lappe, Johannes: Kooperationen wissenschaftlicher Einrichtungen, Baden-Baden: Nomos, 2019, Heidelberger Schriften zum Wirtschaftsrecht und Europarecht; Band 89. Zusammenfassung unter <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/160612223.pdf>
- MoPeG: Gesetz zur Modernisierung des Personengesellschaftsrechts. (Personengesellschaftsrechtsmodernisierungsgesetz – MoPeG) Vom 10. August 2021. Bundesgesetzblatt Jahrgang 2021 Teil I Nr. 53, ausgegeben zu Bonn am 17. August 2021. https://www.bmj.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/DE/Gesetzgebung/BGBl/BgBl_MoPeG.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=3

1.2.6 Further services in the context of the NFDI AAI and the community AAI of the NFDI consortia

Services in the context of the NFDI AAI and the Community AAI of the NFDI consortia that go beyond the scope of services described in this document, or that are explicitly mentioned in this document as being subject to a charge, can be ordered from the following IAM4NFDI project partners (among others):

- DAASI International
 - DAASI International is a private spin-off of a DFN research project that specialises in Open Source Identity and Access Management, including the area of research infrastructures. In this segment, DAASI International offers requirements analyses, expert opinions, concepts, implementation projects, development, help desk support, software maintenance and IAM-as-a-service offerings for various open source products, including the in-house developed didmos.
 - Further information <https://www.daasi.de>
- DFN-Verein
 - The communication services of the German Research Network can be used by all scientific and research institutions, provided they are publicly funded or non-profit organisations. In addition, they are also available to the commercial sector if there is a connection to science and research, e.g. in the case of research collaborations or for access to supercomputers. For possible roles and services of DFN-Verein in the context of the NFDI-AAI, see 1.2.2 above.
 - Further information: <https://www.dfn.de/dienste/>
- FZ-Jülich
 - The Jülich Supercomputing Centre provides state-of-the-art supercomputing resources, IT tools, methods and expertise. Computing time at the highest performance level is made available to researchers in Germany and Europe through an independent peer review process. The JSC currently operates JUWELS, one of the most powerful supercomputers in Europe, and JUNIQ, the first infrastructure for quantum computing.
 - Further information: <https://www.fz-juelich.de/en/ias/jsc>
- Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung Göttingen
 - As the university computing centre for the Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, and as a computing and IT competence centre for the Max Planck Society, the

GWDG offers a wide range of information and communication services for science. In the context of scientific data processing, the GWDG offers IT consulting, the planning, design and implementation of IT projects, provision of infrastructure services, hosting of applications as well as service and support. In the context of the IAM4NFDI project, specific services for customising AcademicID to the individual requirements of NFDI consortia can be commissioned.

- Further information: <https://www.gwdg.de>
- KIT
 - As a central scientific institution at KIT and a centre for data-intensive computing and analysis of large-scale data with high national and international visibility as well as providing innovative and agile IT services at KIT, the Scientific Computing Center (SCC) is the information technology centre of KIT. The SCC researches, teaches and creates innovations in the fields of supercomputing, big data and secure IT federations. It operates large-scale research equipment and provides basic central IT services and enterprise applications. The SCC fulfils the needs of computational science and engineering as well as data-intensive science for users at KIT, state, federal and international level.
 - Further information: <https://www.scc.kit.edu/dienste/index.php>

1.3 Definition of used terms

<i>Term</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
CAAI	Community Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure, i.e. user and group administration operated for an NFDI consortium, including a proxy-capable identity provider.
Client	The contractual partner who uses the services specified in the contract. During the project phase, this role may also be assumed without a dedicated contract.
Community AAI	cf. CAAI.
Contractor	The contractual partner who provides the services specified in contract. During the project phase, appropriate IAM4NFDI project partners may act in this role without a dedicated contract.
Contract value	The contract value is the sum of all payments to be made.
Data backup	Data backup includes all technical and organisational measures to ensure the availability, integrity and consistency of the data and software stored on the IT system and used for processing purposes.
DFN-AAI	The authentication and authorisation infrastructure operated by DFN-Verein. The participation of DFN-AAI in eduGAIN enables interfederation use cases.
Feature update	Update*, which contains new features.

<i>Term</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
Fixed price (all-inclusive)	Unilaterally unchangeable total remuneration owed for the maintenance service*, unless a separate, possibly flat-rate remuneration has been agreed for individual services. Material costs, travelling time, travelling expenses, ancillary costs* are included in the fixed all-inclusive price.*
Malfunction	Impairment of the suitability of the software or the maintenance services* for the contractually agreed use or, in the absence of such an agreement, for the presumed or otherwise customary use. This applies regardless of whether or not there was a need for representation or not and regardless of whether the deviation already existed at the time the contract was concluded.
Malicious software	Software with a function that is undesired by the client* and not agreed upon, and which at least also has the purpose of jeopardising or impairing the availability of data, resources or services, the confidentiality of data or the integrity of data, e.g. viruses, worms, Trojan horses (etc.).
Major release	A release* that contains significant new changes. Significant changes to configuration items and behaviour may occur, so migration can usually only be carried out as part of a consulting project. It is characterised by a version jump of the first digit (e.g. 2.X.X to 3.Y.Y).
Maintenance services	Maintenance services include services to maintain operational readiness, including the provision of new programme versions*.
Minor release	A release* containing minor changes and no enhancements. Apart from justified exceptions, there should be no changes to configuration items. A migration is usually possible as part of a support contract without a separate consulting project. It is characterised by a version jump of the second digit (e.g. X.2.X to X.3.Y).
Patch release	A release* containing only bug fixes but no enhancements. Apart from justified exceptions, there should be no changes to configuration items. A migration is usually possible as part of a support contract without a separate consulting project. It is usually characterised by a version jump of the third digit (e.g. X.Y.2 to X.Y.3).
Project	The IAM4NFDI project as part of Base4NFDI.
Recovery time	Period of time within which the contractor must successfully complete the correction of a malfunction*. This period starts with the receipt of the corresponding notification within the agreed service times* and runs exclusively during the agreed service times*. If a notification is received outside the agreed service times*, the recovery time* starts at the beginning of the next service time*.
Release	New development stage of software that differs significantly from the previous release* in terms of functionality and/or data. The following types of releases are distinguished: patch release*, minor release*, major release*. Another term for release* is version, but this is not used in this text.
Response time	Period of time within which the Contractor must begin to remedy a fault as part of a support contract. This period starts with the receipt of the corresponding notification within the agreed service times* and runs exclusively during the agreed service times*. If a notification is received outside the agreed service times*, the response time* starts at the beginning of the next service time*.

<i>Term</i>	<i>Explanation</i>
Security updates	Updates that are related to a security advisory and only address security issues of the provided service.
Service provider	cf. Contractor.
Service time	Period of time during which the client* is entitled to use contractually owed services from the contractor*.
SLA	Service Level Agreement – Service level agreement for recurring services.
Source code	Code of a program created by software developers using a programming language.
Standard software	Software (program, program module, tool, etc.), including documentation, which has been developed to meet the needs of a majority of clients in the market and which has not been specifically developed by the contractor for the client. An example of this would be the standard CAAI instances provided by the IAM4NFDI project.
Teleservice	Services provided using technical equipment for remote communication from a location outside the site of an IT system.
Ticket system	A ticket system (also known as a trouble ticket system) is an IT system that can be used to receive, classify, acknowledge and process messages and requests with the aim of responding to or resolving problems. It can also be used to track and monitor the progress of tickets. The ticket system acknowledges receipt of a message by repeating its contents.
Update	Bundling of several bug fixes and/or error corrections as well as minor functional improvements and/or adjustments to the software in a single delivery. Change to a new minor release* or patch release*.
Upgrade	Bundling of several bug fixes and/or error corrections and more than minor functional improvements and/or adjustments to the software in a single delivery. Change to a new major release*.
Version	cf. Release*
Workaround	Temporary bypass of a defect and/or malfunction*.

2. General part describing the consulting, support and operating services

2.1 Overview of the products for which services are offered

As part of the IAM4NFDI project, the participating partners offer various services for the NFDI. These services are related to the following products.

2.1.1 Central components

The *NFDI Infrastructure Proxy* is offered as a central component of IAM4NFDI. As an interface between NFDI services and the federated authentication infrastructure (Community AAls,

eduGAIN and Social IdPs), the proxy plays an essential role with critical availability requirements.

The *NFDI Community AA* is also provided centrally. This component is responsible for internal authorisations within NFDI and therefore also has high availability requirements.

At this stage (mid 2024), the exact technical implementation of the two central components has not been finalised.

2.1.2 CAAs

As part of the IAM4NFDI project, the NFDI consortia will be offered four CAAI solutions with a defined feature set and, where appropriate, simple customisation options. All CAAs are Community CAAs as defined in the AARC BPA and fulfil the task of a VO administration. The VO component is essential both for the services directly connected to the CAAs and for the authentication of services via the central proxy. The four CAAI solutions offered are

- AcademicID (GWDG)
- didmos (DAASI International)
- RegApp (KIT)
- Unity (FZ Jülich)

The CAAI solutions offered by the IAM4NFDI project are each to be understood as central, multi-tenant instances. Different communities therefore share a single instance of each CAAI solution, which means that only limited customisation options are available. The exact technical setup and customisation options vary slightly from CAAI to CAAI. The operators of these central CAAI instances offer consulting, support and operating services as part of the IAM4NFDI project, but only to a limited extent. These services are described below. For all CAAI solutions, it is also possible to enter into a separate operating agreement with one of the IAM4NFDI project partners. This is particularly suitable for consortia that require a more customized CAAI (additional functionality, more customisation, etc.) or extended consulting, support or operating services (higher SLAs, etc.).

2.2 Differentiation between consulting, support and operating services

The services offered can be divided into consulting, support and operating services. These three types of services can be broadly distinguished according to the responsibilities involved, the communication processes and the quality of service guaranteed.

Consulting services are negotiated by mutual agreement between the contractor and the client, which includes a joint requirements analysis, a corresponding estimate of the contractor's effort, which is specified in the form of a corresponding offer (time and material based or fixed price offer) and then, after acceptance, carried out cooperatively as a project.

In the case of support services, the service levels offered are defined by the respective service providers. A distinction is made between 1st, 2nd and 3rd level support, with 1st and 2nd level usually being offered in the form of a help desk for end users or administrators, and 3rd level

being offered in the form of a software maintenance contract. In each case, the service is requested by the client on a case-by-case basis, to which the contractor responds within the agreed service levels. In the case of 3rd level support, this goes hand in hand with regular software maintenance work carried out by the contractor.

Operating services are not initiated by the client but are provided automatically by the contractor, e.g. incidents do not need to be reported by the client but are automatically brought to the attention of the contractor by a monitoring system so that the contractor can respond in accordance with the agreed service levels.

3. Consulting services

The IAM4NFDI project provides consulting services to the NFDI, and in particular to its consortia. These services will be provided by Identity & Access Management (IAM) experts and, in addition to consulting, will also include the setup, configuration and integration of the products supported by the IAM4NFDI project, as well as the development of additional functionality required by individual consortia. The consulting services can be used by a group of people designated by the NFDI or the consortia, the IAM administrators.

The basis for these services is a contract resulting from the acceptance of a project offer. During the IAM4NFDI project phase, it is also possible to use consulting services without an individual contract; however, the consulting efforts will have to be adapted to the capacities of the IAM4NFDI project partners or their subsidised project funding. Complex development work would only be possible through dedicated incubator projects or corresponding contracts.

Typical cases for free consulting services during the project phase are

- advice on the selection of an authentication and authorisation solution supported by the IAM4NFDI project for NFDI consortia (Community-AAI, CAAI),
- advice on integrating new applications and identity providers,
- advice on updating and, where necessary, reconfiguring integrated applications and identity providers, and
- consulting on operational and technical issues related to IAM.

Typical cases for consulting services to be commissioned are

- as-is analysis and requirements analysis for a specific research consortium,
- design of a research consortia AAI with specific requirements,
- setup, configuration and customisation of the CAAI instance to meet the specific requirements of a research consortium,
- development of special software features tailored to the needs of a research consortium.

The consulting services can be related to the central components (in particular the integration of new applications as NFDI services on the proxy) as well as to the centrally operated CAAI instances. Dedicated CAAI instances can also be mapped via such consulting services.

4. Support services

General support services can be divided into 1st level (end user support), 2nd level (technical support) and 3rd level (software troubleshooting support).

4.1 General provisions on support services

The contractor shall operate a help desk for a group of persons previously specified in advance by the client. This group of persons can be advised by experts in the field of Identity & Access Management, in particular – but not exclusively – with regard to the operation, maintenance, configuration and integration of the components offered as part of NFDI-AAI. The support service is always initiated by the client. Different service levels have to be agreed upon in advance for different support cases.

4.1.1 Channels

In the event of problems, clients can contact the support team via the following channels:

- Telephone, but only during the contractor's working hours,
- via the contractor's ticket system,
- via the contractor's support e-mail address.

In each case, a corresponding ticket will be created in the contractor's ticket system to document the communication and the work carried out.

4.1.2 Description and solution of the problem

When reporting the problem regardless of the channel, the contractor should describe the problem in a meaningful way, provide background information (context, version numbers, browser software, etc.), a criticality rating, and ideally describe how the error can be reproduced.

This information is entered into the ticket system either automatically when reported through the ticket system or via support email, or manually by the contractor when reported over the phone.

It may be appropriate for the client and contractor to meet via video conference or teleservice software to demonstrate the problem or to provide direct access to the source of the error.

Support is provided by personnel who are qualified to record and initially clarify the fault report. The promised quality of service is maintained throughout the resolution of the problem.

4.2 1st level support

1st level support is designed to assist end users, i.e. when a non-technical person needs help using the software components. A distinction can be made here between users who have a problem accessing an application and administrators who have a problem managing identities, groups and roles. Once the support case shows that the problem is not the fault of the individual but is caused by a misconfiguration or a software bug, 1st-level support can contact 2nd or 3rd level support.

It makes sense for 1st-level support to be provided as close as possible to the end users, so it is advisable for the service provider to be based at the respective research consortium. In principle, however, it is conceivable that a consortium could commission an external service provider to provide 1st level support. The IAM4NFDI project is unable to offer free 1st level support even during the project term.

Typical cases for 1st level support are

- an end user received an error message when authenticating to an NFDI service,
- an end user does not have the expected permissions when accessing a community service

An appropriate introduction or material on the operation of the CAAI, including information on 1st level support, will be provided by each CAAI within the project.

4.3 2nd level support

The purpose of 2nd level support is to assist software administrators. It makes sense for this support to be provided by technicians who are familiar with the software products.

Typical cases for 2nd level support are

- Administrators of an NFDI service have problems with the service connection
- Administrators of a community service want to change the stored encryption certificate in the central CAAI instance

This is to be distinguished from 3rd level support, which involves troubleshooting (bug fixes) in the products offered. IAM4NFDI offers 2nd level support for both the central services and the respective operators for the central CAAI instances during the project term.

4.4 3rd level support

The 3rd level support only includes the maintenance and updating of the source code, but no operating services, except the provision of a test environment. With a software maintenance contract, the contractor guarantees that the software will remain functional on the current operating system versions during the term of the contract and that production-disrupting or security-relevant software errors will be eliminated. This module also includes the delivery of new releases of the software. Part of this support is the provision and utilisation of a test environment. This means that if 3rd level support has been booked, operation of the test environment is automatically included. This is necessary to ensure that the new version of the software remains compatible with the actual configuration. In addition to the regularly performed work, this also includes the acceptance of fault reports resulting from software errors, which is handled in the same way as 1st and 2nd level support cases.

During the project period, 3rd level support for the central CAAI instances and the central components will be offered free of charge, but only on a best-effort basis and not with contractually agreed service levels.

5. Operating services

5.1 Common characteristics of the operating services

The operation of these products includes common services such as

- the provision of services in accordance with the respective service level agreements (SLAs),
- the regular installation of updates,
- availability monitoring for the services, and
- regular backups of the data.

The following sub-chapters contain specific information on this, which differs for the various components of the NFDI-AAI and the Community-AAIs.

5.2 Central components

5.2.1 Infrastructure proxy

5.2.1.1 Overview

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description of the</i>
Name	NFDI infrastructure proxy
Description of the	Connection of resources that should be available across the NFDI (i.e. not just for individual specialist consortia)
Input	User and login information from the IdP components of the CAAls
Processing	Forwarding the input data to the connected resources/services, possibly enriched with additional authorisation information from the Community Attribute Authority (see below)
Output	Input data and any additional authorisation information
Data categories	Personal data, authorisations
Normal utilisation time	24x7
Special service times	Mon-Fri 07-17 h
Regulatory requirements	DSGVO, IT-SIG/BSIG
Maximum tolerable downtime (MTA)	2h (also applies to connected resources)
Service providers who offer operating services	DFN-Verein/DFN-CERT, GWDG(?)

5.2.1.2 Operation

As no decision has yet been made regarding a specific implementation (at the beginning of 2024), information on operation will be provided at a later date. The operation of this component is guaranteed as a free service for the duration of the project.

5.2.2 Community Attribute Authority

5.2.2.1 Overview

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description of the</i>
Name	NFDI Community Attribute Authority
Description of the	Management of overarching, non-community-specific authorisations within the NFDI
Input	Identifiers from the IdP components of the CAAs or the edu-ID system, which can be used to assign users specific authorisations for specific resources
Processing	An identifier attribute can be used by a central(?) NFDI office yet to be defined to assign authorisations to individual users for access to and use of certain NFDI-wide available resources. These authorisations can be retrieved at least by the infrastructure proxy.
Output	Authorisation information
Data categories	Personal data, authorisations
Normal utilisation time	24x7
Special service times	Mon-Fri 07-17 h
Regulatory requirements	DSGVO, IT-SIG/BSIG
Maximum tolerable downtime (MTA)	2h
Service providers who offer operating services	DFN-Verein/DFN-CERT, GWDG(?)

5.2.2.2 Operation

As no decision has yet been made regarding a specific implementation (at the beginning of 2024), information on operation will be provided at a later date. The operation of this component is guaranteed as a free service for the duration of the project.

5.3 Operating services for the community AAs

5.3.1 AcademicID

5.3.1.1 Overview

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description of the</i>
Name	AcademicID Identity & Access Management System
Description of the	Management of identities, accounts and resources; authentication and authorisation infrastructure for protocols such as SAML, OIDC, ADFS
Input	User and login information

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description of the</i>
Processing	Automatic assignment of authorisations and attributes; login data is checked for authentication and authorisation, the user data is forwarded to the respective service,
Output	Personal data such as surname, first name and email address, as well as any authorisations, are passed on to the connected service.
Data categories	Personal data
Normal utilisation time	24x7
Special service times	Mon-Fri 07-17 h
Regulatory requirements	DSGVO, IT-SIG/BSIG
Maximum tolerable downtime (MTA)	IDM: 48h, SSO: 4h
Service providers who offer operating services	GWDG

5.3.1.2 Operation

The AcademicID IAM system is operated and administered by the GWDG IAM team. Linux is used as the operating system for the IAM server. Access to the system for administrative activities is exclusively via SSH with individual SSH keys via a separate VPN network.

Maintenance work and updates are subject to the GWDG's change management process and take place during the GWDG's regular maintenance window. All changes are checked in advance on test systems and released by the IAM team in accordance with the dual control principle. Manufacturer updates are checked for integrity after downloading using checksums.

The administrators of the IAM system have subscribed to the relevant mailing lists for the operating systems and software components used and receive information on bug fixes and updates. Critical security updates are installed as quickly as possible.

A comprehensive data backup and- restore concept (backup/restore) is in place for the IAM system.

System and event-based logs are kept (logging), whereby passwords are not logged. Furthermore, the availability of all systems in productive use is monitored by a monitoring system. Performance monitoring is also carried out for capacity planning.

Faults can be reported via support ticket, e-mail, telephone or chat. Emergency documentation is available for rectifying faults and restarting the system. The IAM team is part of the GWDG's general alerting plan.

The regulatory requirements of the GDPR are met when operating the IAM system. A risk analysis and an allocation to damage impact categories are available.

The IAM system is included in the scope of the GWDG's ISO 9001 and ISO 27001 certifications; detailed operating concepts are stored in the GWDG's Quality and Information Security Management System (QMS/ISMS).

5.3.2. didmos

5.3.2.1 Overview

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description of the</i>
Name	didmos IAM System as CAAI
Description of the	Management of identities, accounts and roles; central policy decision point for managing authorisation to resources via roles; authentication and authorisation infrastructure for protocols such as SAML, OIDC with the option of managing both consortium accounts internally (e.g. for homeless users) and shadow accounts, i.e. identities that authenticate themselves via a CampusIdP or any other external IdP.
Input	User and login information
Processing	Automatic assignment of authorisations and attributes; login data is checked for authentication and authorisation, the user data is forwarded to the respective service,
Output	Personal data such as surname, first name and email address, as well as any authorisations, are passed on to the connected service.
Data categories	Personal data
Normal utilisation time	24x7
Special service times	Mon-Fri 8:30-17:30
Regulatory requirements	DSGVO, IT-SIG/BSIG
Maximum tolerable downtime (MTA)	IDM: 48h, SSO: 4h
Service providers who offer operating services	DAASI International

5.3.2.2 Operation

didmos is produced by DAASI International and is available to everyone as open source. In addition to further development and dedicated client feature development, DAASI International also offers software maintenance contracts, help desk and didmos as-a-service both on-premise and as a full cloud solution. As part of IAM4NFDI, DAASI operates a multi-client instance (didmos4NFDI) that can be used free of charge by all NFDI research consortia and offers free advice if a consortium wants to set up and operate the software itself. Implementation and customisation services can also be requested free of charge to a limited extent during the project phase via an incubator project. After the end of the project, all these services, including

the operation of an individual instance as-a-service and SLA-proven help desk hours, can be sustainably obtained at reduced hourly rates for academic institutions.

Linux is used as the operating system for didmos. Administrative access is via SSH with personalised SSH keys and is restricted to DAASI IP ranges. Maintenance work and updates are subject to the change management process of DAASI International and take place in regular maintenance windows. All changes are checked in advance on test systems and only then released. The administrators of the IAM system have subscribed to the relevant mailing lists for the operating systems and software components used and receive information on bug fixes and updates via these lists. Critical security updates to the operating system are automatically installed within a day and monitored.

A comprehensive data backup and- restore concept (backup/restore) is in place for the IAM system. System and event-based logs are kept (logging), whereby passwords are not logged. Furthermore, the availability of all productively used systems is monitored by a monitoring system. Faults can be reported via a support ticket, e-mail or telephone. Emergency documentation is available for rectifying faults and restarting the system. The regulatory requirements of the GDPR are met when operating the IAM system.

5.3.3 RegApp

5.3.3.1 Overview

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description of the</i>
Name	RegApp IAM system as CAAI
Description of the	Provisioning and deprovisioning of user identities, accounts and group memberships; transparent connection of SAML federations; SSO protocol proxy OIDC ↔ SAML; infrastructure proxy for LDAP services; storage/administration/provisioning of SSH keys; multifactor authentication for web and non-web services
Input	User and login information
Processing	Automatic assignment of authorisations and attributes; login data is checked for authentication and authorisation, the user data is forwarded to the respective service,
Output	Personal data such as surname, first name and email address, as well as any authorisations, are passed on to the connected service.
Data categories	Personal data
Normal utilisation time	24x7
Special service times	Mon-Fri 7:00-15:00
Regulatory requirements	DSGVO, IT-SIG/BSIG
Maximum tolerable downtime (MTA)	

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description of the</i>
Service providers who offer operating services	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

5.3.3.2 Operation

RegApp is a federated open-source identity management system that is being developed primarily at the Scientific Computing Centre (SCC) at KIT. The currently installed solution enables more than 38,000 registered users from various research institutions, including the Helmholtz Association and universities, to log in to various services.

All RegApp instances are operated at the SCC. VMware-virtualised servers with Linux as the operating system are used for operation. Administrative access to the system is exclusively via key-based SSH from the KIT network with individual keys.

The RegApp is an in-house development based on Java (Quarkus, Jakarta 10) and Angular as well as a common Postgres database system. All self-written code and all integrated third-party libraries first run through a CI pipeline before they are made available on test systems. They are then installed on the production instances with a time delay. The configuration is stored in SCC's own configuration management system and version-managed in a Git repository.

Operating system package updates are installed regularly and SSL certificates are renewed automatically. Local monitoring of the services also provides information about pending updates, necessary restarts and unusual load situations. The services are integrated into the SCC-wide service monitoring so that administrators are immediately informed of any outages. Restarts to update security-relevant packages are only carried out outside normal working hours and usually only take a few minutes. Restarts and software updates are uninterrupted and go unnoticed by end users, as both the RegApp and the database system are clustered behind a multi-level load distribution concept. The individual components are distributed across the two KIT sites with a physical distance of 10 kilometres and two independent internet connections.

Snapshots of the virtual machines and file-based backups of the databases are created daily. Log files and relevant system events are collected in a central logging system and saved there in accordance with the retention periods. Passwords are not logged; the logs and events of the KIT-CERT are analysed automatically to detect anomalies and attacks.

Problems and faults can be reported via a ticket system or by e-mail.

5.3.4 Unity

5.3.4.1 Overview

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description of the</i>
Name	Unity IDM
Description of the	Management of identities, accounts and group memberships; authentication and authorisation infrastructure for SAML and OAuth2/OIDC protocols

<i>Field</i>	<i>Description of the</i>
Input	User and login information
Processing	Automatic assignment of authorisations and attributes; login data is checked for authentication and authorisation, the user data is forwarded to the respective service,
Output	Personal data such as surname, first name and email address, as well as any authorisations, are passed on to the connected service.
Data categories	Personal data
Normal utilisation time	24x7
Special service times	Mon-Fri 08-16 hrs, except public holidays and bridging days
Regulatory requirements	DSGVO, IT-SIG/BSIG
Maximum tolerable downtime (MTA)	
Service providers who offer operating services	Jülich Research Centre

5.3.4.2 Operation

Unity IDM is operated and managed by the Data Management and Analytics Group at the JSC of Forschungszentrum Jülich. Virtual servers with Linux as the operating system are used for operation. Administrative access to the system is exclusively via key-based SSH from the research centre's network with individual keys and user accounts.

All updates are first tested on a separate system by the administrators and only transferred to the systems in operation once they have successfully run through the entire, constantly growing test catalogue. The updates are rolled out to the systems in two stages. Firstly, the systems that are made available to the developers of connected services for testing are updated, followed with a time delay by the systems with which the users log in. A configuration management system is used to manage the configuration of the servers and services. This ensures that the services correspond to the defined configuration. Changes to the managed configurations are only accepted and applied after successfully passing a syntax check.

Package updates for the operating system are installed regularly. In addition, regular vulnerability checks are carried out and the administrators are informed of any vulnerabilities found. The local monitoring of the services also provides information about pending updates and necessary restarts. Restarts are only carried out outside normal working hours (8:00-19:00) or during announced maintenance windows. A restart outside normal working hours is used to update security-relevant packages and only takes a few minutes.

The underlying database management system creates daily exports. These are backed up daily along with all other relevant parts of the server. Administrators are informed of failed backups the following day. In addition, additional database exports are created and backup points are created before Unity IDM updates or major system updates.

System and event-based logs are kept on the systems. No passwords are logged. The logs are stored or deleted in accordance with the specifications. In addition, the system is monitored by monitoring systems and the administrators are informed of any problems.

Problems and faults can be reported via ticket systems or by e-mail. There is also documentation of the most common problems with steps for solving them.

6. Annexes

It is planned to develop the following annexes with early adopters and make them available as generalised templates for further contracts with NFDI consortia.

6.1 Service Level Agreements

6.2 Specifics of the individual service providers' consulting services

6.3 Specific support services of the individual service providers

6.4 Specifics of the operating services of the individual service providers

7. Contract templates

It is planned to draw up the following contracts with early adopters and make them available as generalised templates for further contracts with NFDI consortia.

7.1 General templates

7.1.1 EVB-IT contract

7.2 Specific systems of the individual service providers

7.2.1 AVV

7.2.2 Technical and organisational measures